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Trade Receivables Management and Liquidity of Oil Service Companies (Case in Rivers State, Nigeria)

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Abstract: This research study was an investigation into the relationship between Trade Receivables Management and Organizations' Liquidity, as made consistent with survey results from 10 Oil Servicing Companies in Nigeria, for the periods 2013-2017. Trade Receivables Management in dimensions of Average Collection Period (ACP) and Account Receivables Turnover (ART) constituted our independent variable, whereas Organizations' Liquidity in dimensions of Current Ratio (CR) and Quick Ratio (QR) made up our dependent variable. The study employed Measures of Central Tendencies, Measures of Dispersion, Pearson Product Moment Correlation, Analysis of Variance and multiple regression techniques to analyze data collected from annual financial reports in the denominations of Income Statements and Statements of Financial Position. The results of the study, as computed via the SPSS, show that Average Collection Period (ACP) and Account Receivables Turnover (ART) [Measures of the Independent Variable,] had negative statistically significant relationships with Current Ratio and Quick Ratio respectively [Measures of the Dependent Variable]. Research results were further interpreted to mean that high levels of trade receivables would reduce liquidity of oil servicing companies in the long run in Nigeria. The study therefore recommended that oil service companies focus more on reducing their average collection periods in order to improve their Current Ratio position; and since Account Receivables Turnover exerts a negative influence of 10.6% as opposed to the 0.5% decrease brought about by ACP to Quick ratios, Oil servicing companies should improve on their means for retrieving account receivables faster within the year to improve their quick ratios.

Keywords: Trade receivable, Liquidity, Credit, Current ratio, Quick ratio.

1. INTRODUCTION

Trade receivable, on its own, is one business transaction type which refers to the way of dealing with amounts of money that are owed a business by its customer(s). Khurana. A. (2007). On the statement of financial position of a company, trade receivables are disclosed to signify the amount of money that a

customer(s) owe(s) it, and they are conventionally shown as positive value-adding figures to the overall financial welfare of the company as at the financial position date. Trade receivables are also referred to as account receivables in the professional sense, which makes the concept a little less ambiguous when necessity warrants referencing other related works. As this is a debt related amount, it is always seen appearing under the category of current assets on the statement of financial position of the company.

Following recognized accounting practice, a trade receivables transaction is generally carried out by means of an invoice, which is sent to the customer with the aim of informing him of the duration within which the debt amount must be paid off. The term “within which the debt has to be paid” may be thirty days, forty-five days, sixty days, or even as much as ninety days. However, the duration of the debt depends entirely on the debtor and the creditor.

Currently the financial accounting standards governing treatment of this item are IFRS 9 (International Financial Reporting Standards)/ IAS 39 (International Accounting Standards) & IFRS 15 Revenue from contracts with customers.

Effective accounts receivable management is important and strategic; it affects the financial performance of a firm and a firm’s value. A firm’s competency to synchronize cash inflows with cash outflows in formulating a cash flow management strategy is important to a firm’s financial performance. The core mandate of trade receivables management lies in shareholder wealth maximization. Liquidity on the other hand is a necessity for the survival of the firm. While comparing liquidity with profitability, liquidity gets higher priority. No firm will continue to exist if it has no liquidity. Firms which do not make profit may be treated as under par; but not having liquidity may cease to operate over a period (Agarwal & Mishra 2007). Liquidity is defined by the relative ease, cost, and speed with which an asset can be converted into cash (Bodie & Merton, 2000). The objective of liquidity management, in the words of Gallinger & Healey (1991), is to provide for adequate availability and safekeeping of corporate funds under varied economic conditions in order to help achieve the desired corporate objectives of shareholder’s wealth maximization.

If one were to reduce business to the simplest terms, one would probably call it the selling of goods by one person, and the buying of those same goods by another. Thus, whether we pay cash or run up a tab while doing business, money would rightly have been said to have changed hands during the course of business transaction. But this is seldom so in real world situation. By defunct, business practice today, in accordance with commercial advancement, should or even must carry out trading on credit. As long as there is competition in the industry, selling on credit becomes inevitable.

A business will lose its customers to competitors if it does not extend credit to them. Thus, investment in accounts (trade) receivables may not be a matter of choice but a matter of survival. However, excessive level of accounts receivable ratio on profitability may lead to a negative effect. This is because if a firm has so many debtors, they may become short of cash which may lead to difficulty in settling their very own short-term financial obligations. This of course constitutes a problem requiring both research and practical attention.

Receivables management, in context of our study, is important to the profitability of an oil-oriented organization. Oil resource is an important energy resource in the world, with its prices purely dictated by OPEC strategies.

Some companies that are still in business and are also listed in the Nigerian stock exchange cannot pay dividends to their shareholders anymore. Some Nigeria workers have further been forcefully thrown out of employment. Some of these companies with high rate of returns have gradually turned out to be failures and eventually frustrated out of office. (Okpe et al 2015). These and many more are the expressed or implicit manifestations of screaming records of trade receivables and form the scope of our problems for this study.

In line with our above stated problems hence, the objective of this study is to properly establish the relationship between trade receivables management and the liquidity of organizations in a bid to see which aspects of both exerts a negative influence on the other and proffering solutions to the identified down sides. To achieve this purpose, the following hypotheses, stated in the null, would be tested:

- HO1 The Average Collection period of Oil Service Companies have no significant relationship with their Current Ratios as a measure of Liquidity;
- HO2 The Account Receivables Turnover of Oil Service Companies have no significant relationship with their Quick Ratios as a measure of Liquidity;
- HO3 The Average Collection Period of Oil Service Companies have no significant relationship with their Quick Ratios as a measure of Liquidity; and
- HO4 The Account Receivables Turnover of Oil Service Companies have no significant relationship with their Current Ratios as a measure of Liquidity.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1. Theoretical Overview

Trade receivables are a component of Working capital and thus we shall mainly discuss Working capital theories relating with Trade payables and other theories on trade receivables. We shall here consider three (3) of such theories:

- Risk & Return Theory;
- Resource-based Theory; and
- Agency Theory

2.1.1. Risk & Return Theory

Risk handling is the main component considered in making financial decision this includes how risks can be measured and how the required return associated with a given risk level is determined. Modigliani & Pogue (1974). For any investment in finance to be considered an analysis of both risk associated and Returns expected must be determined. There are normally two types of risk behaviors associated with trade receivables management. , that is, conservative (risk averse) trade Receivables management policy and aggressive (risk seekers) trade receivables management policy. While more aggressive trade receivables policies are associated with higher returns and risk; where risk is underestimated and gains are overestimated. On the other hand conservative trade receivables behavior offer both lower risk and returns, where risks are overestimated while gains are underestimated Gardner et al., (1986)

The risk and return theory relates to TRM in terms of decisions requiring the trade-off between profitability and liquidity. If a firm decides to go for liquidity it will have to forgo its profitability. This will result to low sales since it will prefer to sell its goods on cash basis and avoid selling on trade credit. Improving its liquidity position but lowering its profitability.

On the other hand if a firm chooses to go for profitability it will have to forgo its liquidity resulting in increased sales and reduced liquidity. Since sales on credit will directly increase profit but will reduce cash flow associated with cash sales. A proper trade off should be maintained between the profitability and liquidity of the firm through proper management of trade receivables. Since an excess of Trade receivables will result to increased cost of collection which is associated with bad debts, high financing costs, low liquidity and ultimately low profits. A shortage of trade receivables will result to low turnover and thus low profitability which will in turn result to reduced liquidity in the long run. The credit control Manager will make decisions using this theory to enhance the firm's profitability.

2.1.2. Resource-based Theory

The Resource-Based View (RBV) of the firm puts forward the theory that resources are the main drivers of a firm's superior performance. It argues that every firm should take a look inside its processes to find the competitive advantage resources rather than observing its competitive environment which it has no control over. Barney (1995). Resources in this perspective can be classified broadly into intangible and tangible resources. They consist of assets, capabilities, organizational processes and information which the firm utilizes in order to achieve profitability. The RBV of the firm emphasizes those valuable, rare imperfectly non-imitate able and non-substitutable firms' resources result in competitive advantage. It states that resources that are entirely controlled or owned by a firm should be cultivated so as to enhance

their contribution to the organizations competitive advantage in its industrial context. The firm has few productive resources. Productivity requires coordination and cooperation of a number of resources so as to achieve a certain activity or task. Thus resources greatly determine a firm’s capability. In context of Trade Receivables Management (TRM), the credit control manager has specific resources that facilitate and ensure the identification of new chance or opportunity (customer sales), effective bringing together of resources and recovery of receivables as and when they become due to ensure proper management of trade receivable and eventually the firms profitability.

2.1.3. Agency Theory

The definition of an agency relationship is a relationship in which one (or more) person hereby known as a principal(s) contracts another person known as an agent to render a service on their behalf in this case at some level of the authority to make a decision of the principal is delegated to the agent Meckling & Jensen (1976). The agency relationship comes about when two or more parties where one who is referred to as an agent, acts on behalf of, acts for, or as a representative for another hereby known as the principal which involves decision making. Agency theory especially applies in the finance field as it considers issues such as conflict of interest, incentive problems and how to solve such problems. It suggests how to establish a normative relationship between the principal and agent. The establishment of a contractual relationship involving the agent and the principal acts as an incentive for the agent to make decisions in which the principal’s welfare is maximized. Meckling & Jensen(1976)

This theory relates to trade receivables management from the perspective of trade receivables managers or otherwise referred to as the Credit Control Manager. The credit control manager is the firm’s shareholders agent and makes all paramount decisions that concern the receivables of the business. His decisions have a very big impact on the shareholders wealth. This is due to the fact that if he fails to sell to creditworthy customers, there would result reduced revenues due to low sales.

On the other hand, the credit manager might decide to sell unknowingly to un-creditworthy customers, which will result in an increase in bad debt expenses and thus reducing the shareholders wealth. The agency theory seeks to find a balance between the agent (Credit Control Manager) and the Principal (Shareholders) such that the Credit Control Manager’s decisions always have the top interests of the shareholders at heart.

2.2. Conceptual Overview

Our conceptual framework could be overviewed in the figure below:

Fig. 1: Conceptual Framework of Trade Receivables Management and Organization Liquidity, showing Independent (Left), Moderating (Middle) and Dependent (Right) Variables respectively.

2.2.1. The Concept of Trade Receivables Management

Credit facilities are one of the most significant drivers of business growth in terms of sales volumes. Trade receivables are a direct product of Credit sales. These are current assets arising from sale of merchandise or provision of services on credit to customers Accounting Coach(2009). They are the amounts we expect our customers to pay in the near future. Trade receivables are receivables that arise in the normal selling of goods to customers, while non-trade receivables includes items such as interest receivables, insurance claims receivables or receivables from employees. In this study I will only concentrate on Trade receivables. Businesses must ensure proper management of trade receivables to avoid finding their liquidity under considerable strain and to remain profitable Lynch (2005). Receivables constitute a big investment in the firm current assets. They should therefore be evaluated just like capital expenditures for their net present values. Emery et al.(2004).

Sales are stimulated by offering trade receivables since customers can assess the quality of products and services before paying for them. However we should also put into consideration the fact that trade receivables involve funds and hence should be seen as an opportunity cost. These characteristics of accounts receivables such as the element of risk, futurity and economic value necessitate the need for an efficient management of trade receivables.

According to Berry and Jarvis (2006), before a firm comes up with a credit policy that will optimize the trade receivables level it has to weigh the options between the increased sales revenue and the additional administrative costs associated with the increased trade receivables. It should also consider the level of risk its ready to face while extending credit to its customers since some may be unable to pay when their debt falls due. They should also not ignore the extra investment in debt management such as extra staff.

Gill (2010) asserts that the main task of accounts receivables management is to optimize the balance between management of cash-flow components. Cash-flow management is basically involved with planning and control of cash inflows and outflows in any firm. It also involves the holding of the optimal level of cash by a firm at any point in time.

According to Samilogu & Demrgunes (2008) any firm with a proper trade receivables management system is able to increase profitability due to a reduction in transactions costs involved in raising extra funds due to liquidity issues.

Ahmet (2012). Accounts receivable as a component of cash flow directly effects profitability of any firm. Cash-flow management can be described as the management of cash inflows and cash outflows in and out of the firm. The main component of management of cash flow includes inventory, trade receivables, planning of cash-flow and trade payables.

Management of trade credit is commonly known as Management of Receivables. Receivables are one of the three primary components of working capital, the other being inventory and cash. Receivables occupy second important place after inventories and thereby constitute a substantial portion of current assets in several firms. The capital invested in receivables is almost of the same amount as that invested in cash and inventories.

Receivables, also termed as trade credit or debtors are component of current assets. When a firm sells its product in credit, account receivables are created. Account receivable is the money receivable in some future date for the credit sale of goods and services at present. These days, most business transactions are in credit. Most companies, when they face competition, use credit sales as an important tool for sales promotion. As a sales promotion tool, credit sale enhances firm's sales revenue and ultimately pushes up the profitability. But after the credit sale has been made, the actual collection of cash may be delayed for months. As these late payments stretch out over time, they may cause substantial drop in a company's profit margin. Since the extension of credit involves both cost and benefits, the firm's manager must be able to measure them to determine the ultimate effect of credits sales. In this prospective, we define the receivable management as the aspect of a firm's current assets management, which is concerned with determining optimum credit policy associated to a firm, such that the benefit from extension of credit is greater than the cost of maintaining investment in accounts receivables.

2.2.2. The Concept of Organization Liquidity

Liquidity is defined by the relative ease, cost, and speed with which an asset can be converted into cash (Bodie & Merton, 2000).

According to Shim and Siegel (2000) accounting liquidity is the company's capacity to liquidate maturing short-term debt (within one year). Maintaining adequate liquidity is much more than a corporate goal, it is a condition without which the continuity of a business is at risk.

The main objective of companies operating in capitalist economies or mixed economies, as we are, is to achieve an appropriate return over the amount of risk accepted by the shareholders. After all, profit is the propulsive element of any investments in different projects.

The assessment of profitability is usually done through the ROA (Return on Assets = Net Income / Total Assets) and ROE (Return on Equity = Net Income / Equity), which is the ultimate measure of economic success (Damilola, 2006).

Liquidity management is a concept that is receiving serious attention all over the world especially with the current financial situations and the state of the world's economy. The concern of business owners and managers all over the world is to devise a strategy of managing their day to day operations in order to meet their obligations as they fall due and increase profitability and shareholder's wealth.

The liquidity of a company is measured with use of some financial ratios referred to as liquidity ratios. This group of ratios measures the ability of the firm to meet its current obligations (Liabilities). Analysis of liquidity needs the preparation of cash budgets and cash flow statement; but liquidity ratio, by establishing a relationship between cash and other current assets to current obligations, provided a quick measure of liquidity (Pandy 2005).

2.2.3. The Concept of Average Collection Period (ACP/DCP)

This could also be referred to as Debtor's Collection Period (DCP). It is a ratio which shows the number of days, weeks or months it takes an organization to recover its credit sales. The shorter the period of recovery, the better for the organization. Account receivables with longer recoverable period possess the risk of bad debt for the company and also affect liquidity in the short run (Owolabi and Obida 2012)

DCP (Debtor's Collection Period) ratio is calculated by dividing Trade debtors by Turnover and multiplying the result by 365 days in the year:

$$DCP = \frac{\text{Average Trade Debtors} \times 365 \text{ Days}}{\text{Turnover}}$$

The average collection period is the number of days on average that it takes a company to collection of its credit accounts or its accounts receivables. In other words, the average collection period of accounts receivable is the average number of days required to convert receivables into cash.

2.2.4. The Concept of Account Receivables Turnover (ART)

Trade debtors are expected to be converted into cash within a short period time and are included in current assets. A high debtors' turnover ratio designates a reasonable credit policy, higher sales, over investment in debtors or slow paying debtors. The higher the value of debtors' turnover the more efficient is the management of debtors or more liquid the debtors are. In the same way, low debtors' turnover ratio implies inefficient management of debtors. It is the reliable measure of the time of cash flow from credit sales. (Bhunias.A. & Palash.B 2015).

As will be employed in this research work, the formula for calculating this ratio is given as:

$$ART = \frac{\text{Credit Revenue}}{\text{Trade Receivables}}$$

2.2.5. The Concept of Current Ratio (CR)

Current ratio is an assessment of overall liquidity and is basically used to make the interpretation of liquidity of firm in the short-run. A relatively high current ratio is a pointer that the firm has huge liquidity and has the ability to pay the matured obligation in time.

The current ratio is an indication of the extent with which current liabilities, which must be paid within a year, are covered by current assets by current assets. It is a firm's market liquidity and ability to meet creditor's demands. Acceptable current ratios vary from industry to industry. If a company's current ratio is in this range, then it is generally considered to have good short-term financial strength. If current liabilities exceed current assets (the current ratio is below one), then the company may have problems meeting its short-term obligations. If the current ratio is too high, then the company may not be efficiently using its current assets or its short-term financing facilities. This may also indicate problems in their liquidity management processes. It is expressed mathematically as:

$$\text{Current ratio} = \frac{\text{Current asset}}{\text{Current liability}}$$

2.2.6. The Concept of Quick Ratio (QR)

Also known as Acid-test or Liquid ratio, this ratio is an indicator of the company's ability to meet its current liabilities as they become due, given that the company's inventory and prepaid expenses are excluded. Quick ratio is a more specific test of liquidity than current ratio. A high quick ratio is an indication that the company has liquidity and will be able to meet its current liabilities in time. But a low quick ratio shows that liquidity position of the company is not good. It is mathematically expressed as:

$$\text{Quick Ratio} = \frac{\text{Current Assets} - (\text{Inventory} + \text{Prepaid Expenses})}{\text{Current Liabilities}}$$

2.3. Empirical Overview

2.3.1. Other Literary Consideration

This entails the analysis of past studies which are similar to the one being conducted with an aim of obtaining knowledge as to what information and other available materials for operational purposes. This will make it possible for the researcher to spell out his own research problem in meaningful context.

Bougheas et al. (2009) focused his research on the reaction of trade receivables to changes in risk, inventory cost, liquidity and profitability. Other authors surveyed the effect of optimal debtors' management, i.e. the best way of managing trade receivables that result to maximization of a firm's profit. Research conducted by Deloof (2003), where he studied 1009 large Belgian non-financial companies for the time 1992-1996, found a significantly negative relationship between accounts receivables turnover and profitability.

Lazaridis & Tryfonidis (2006) also explored the relationship between accounts receivables management and profitability for the companies listed in the Athens Securities Exchange taking into consideration a sample of one hundred and thirty one listed firms. The researcher conducted the study between the years 2001-2004. When a regression analysis was conducted on the results it showed a statistically significant association between profitability (which was measured using the gross operating profit), and the Cash Conversion Cycle (CCC). He concluded that optimization of the CCC by managers could increase shareholder value. There was also a statistically significant relationship between the firm's profitability and efficiency of its trade receivables.

In ksenija (2013), he investigates how public companies listed at the regulated market in the republic of Serbia manage their accounts receivable during recession times. A sample of 108 firms is used. The accounts receivables policies are examined in the crisis period of 2008-2011. The short-term effects are tested and the study shows that between accounts receivables and two dependent variables on profitability, return on total asset and operating profit margin, there is a positive but no significant relation. This suggests that the impact of receivables on firm's profitability is changing times of crisis.

2.3.2. Identified Research Knowledge Gaps to be filled by Study

Our identified knowledge gaps are varied and will be evenly paragraphed.

First, it is very much clear from the above literature review that we are getting mixed observations about the liquidity and profitability positions of different companies. In some cases we have observed that companies have sound liquidity positions, that is, having positive working capital positions and they are doing well in terms of profitability. However in a few cases we have examined that inspite of having negative working capital, they are doing well in terms of profitability. That means, they are not at all liquid firms, but they still earn huge amount of profits.

Secondly, based on their varied perspectives and methods of evaluation, relationship between trade receivables and liquidity is seldom researched upon. In other words, the subject is not properly researched. As such, this research study stands to settle these deficiencies to a considerable degree.

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

3.1. Research Design

The study will adopt descriptive survey design so as to get accurate and detailed information to find out the major characteristics of variables associated with the case under study. This will allow for the discovery of causes even when the variables cannot be controlled

3.2. Population of the Study

A study population is the entire accessible group of persons that is of interest to the researcher or meets the criteria the researcher is interested in studying. Population covers all 16 oil servicing companies in Port-Harcourt listed in the Nigerian Stock Exchange.

3.3. Sample Size

For the purpose of this research, attention shall be drawn only to ten (10) oil service companies, as listed in the Nigerian Stock Exchange. These include, but are not limited to:

Table 1: Sampled Oil Service Companies

S/NO	OIL COMPANY
1.	CONOIL PLC
2.	ETERNA PLC
3.	FORTE OIL
4.	CAPITAL OIL
5.	MOBIL
6.	TOTAL NIGERIA
7.	JAPPAUL OIL
8.	OANDO PLC
9.	MRS OIL PLC
10.	SEPLAT PETROLEUM

3.4. Method of Data Collection

Purely secondary data will be used in this process. As such, published financial reports of the sampled oil servicing companies, as referenced from the Nigerian Stock Exchange (NSE) platform, will constitute instruments for data generation and analysis.

3.5. Data Analysis Technique

We already stated that our analysis will purely be descriptive .The panel methodology to be adopted will be aided by Excel 2010 and IBM SPSS Version 20 software. Descriptive statistics shall contain measures of central tendencies (Mean, median, mode) and dispersion (Standard deviation, variance). Bivariate

Pearson correlation, multiple regressions and Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) will be used to test the significance of the effect of Trade Receivables Management on Organization Liquidity as touching the sampled oil service companies tabulated in our sample size dimension above. The study will employ econometric models to test correlation between proxies as operationalized in the previous chapter. The model is represented by the regression formulae below;

$$y = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + \beta_3 X_3 + \dots + \beta_q X_q + \varepsilon(x)$$

Where y is the dependent variable to be correlated. β_0 is the constant/intercept, ε or x is the error term, β_1 to β_q are the coefficients of the independent variables while X_1 to X_q are the independent variables.

Since there are two (2) independent variables in the study to be correlated to the dependent, we have the following off-shoot models:

$$CR = \beta_0 + \beta_1 ACP + \beta_2 ART + \varepsilon \dots \dots \dots (1)$$

$$QR = \beta_0 + \beta_1 ACP + \beta_2 ART + \varepsilon \dots \dots \dots (2)$$

Where:

CR = Current Ratio

QR = Quick Ratio

ACP = Average Collection Period

ART = Account Receivables Turnover.

4. RESEARCH RESULTS

Deductions and findings from study here take root from review and ratio analysis of financial statements. Within this light, the books of account relevant enough for data generation covers only the income statement and the statement of financial position of the ten (10) sampled oil servicing companies. This section would be sub-divided into statistical data derivation from which to develop research findings and research results derived thereof upon use via computation by the SPSS.

4.1. Calculation of Research Data Used in Establishing Findings

We shall here consider each company individually and extract relevant data from their financial reports upon which to advance findings. Each of these companies' data shall contain every variable required to generate our ratios and average collection periods alike.

Using a 5-year span (from 2013-2017), the data beneath apply to variables falling within the dependent and independent categories for the different companies, computed via Excel 2010. Worthy of note is that certain companies within the sample were still at infancy within the periods relevant and lag a year or two behind others in the commencement of operations and/or listing on the Nigerian Stock Exchange platform. As much as possible however, the researchers considered this a factor when mapping out a common time frame for study and will use available data most validly, without prejudice to the first financial years of these affected companies, where values are not supplied (especially the opening accounts receivables) due to one or both of the reasons given.

1) CONOIL PLC.

Table 2: Data on Variables relating to Conoil Plc.

OIL SERVICE COMPANY		CONOIL PLC				
RESEARCH FACTORS	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	
Credit Revenue	159,537,133	128,352,674	82,919,220	85,023,546	115,513,246	
Trade Receivables	38,117,934	44,447,855	28,024,349	16,383,929	25,866,860	
Account Receivables Turnover Ratio	4.185356242	2.887713569	2.958827697	5.189447903	4.465684896	
Inventory	10,635,426	5,516,195	5,550,287	5,255,596	5,661,155	
Prepaid Expenses	160,889	246,004	189,116	135,890	69,230	
Sum	10,796,315	5,762,199	5,739,403	5,391,486	5,730,385	
Current Liabilities	63,457,616	69,966,552	50,444,300	51,367,783	44,045,149	
Quick Ratio	1.038559044	1.080601199	1.148096138	1.142336316	1.172470026	
current Assets	76,700,796	81,368,139	63,654,309	64,070,770	57,372,002	
Current Liabilities	63,457,616	69,966,552	50,444,300	51,367,783	44,045,149	
Current Ratio	1.208693311	1.16295768	1.261873175	1.247294827	1.302572549	
Opening Account Receivables	58,384,396	38,117,934	44,447,855	28,024,348	16,383,929	
Closing Account Receivables	38,117,934	44,447,855	28,024,349	16,383,929	25,866,860	
Sum of Account Receivables	96,502,330	82,565,789	72,472,204	44,408,277	42,250,789	
Average Account Receivables	48251165	41282894.5	36236102	22204138.5	21125394.5	
Annual Amount (*365)	17611675225	15068256493	13226177230	8104510553	7710768993	
Credit Sales	159,537,133	128,352,674	82,919,220	85,023,546	115,513,246	
Average Collection Period	110.3923262	117.3972931	159.5067733	95.32077799	66.75224928	

2) ETERNA PLC.

Table 3: Data on Variables relating to Eterna Plc.

OIL SERVICE COMPANY		ETERNA PLC				
RESEARCH FACTORS	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	
Credit Revenue	98,296,903	82,832,117	92,669,238	107,536,032	173,611,081	
Trade Receivables	7,921,092	6,101,462	18,365,420	13,283,455	27,908,580	
Account Receivables Turnover Ratio	12.40951412	13.57578184	5.045854546	8.095486603	6.220706356	
Inventory	3273828	2905174	1217501	4068467	6487073	

Prepaid Expenses	109,995	98,218	191,299	167,498	183,137
Sum	3,383,823	3,003,392	1,408,800	4,235,965	6,670,210
Current Liabilities	9182543	8773471	17330038	18135432	33111169
Quick Ratio	0.927901018	1.000110105	1.166406444	1.124898982	0.978311457
current Assets	11904314	11777829	21622668	24636494	39063246
Current Liabilities	9182543	8708742	17330038	18135432	33111169
Current Ratio	1.296407106	1.352414505	1.247698822	1.358472961	1.1797604
Opening Account Receivables	25493986	7866092	6101462	18365420	13283455
Closing Account Receivables	7,921,092	6,101,462	18,365,420	13,283,455	27,908,580
Sum of Account Receivables	33,415,078	13,967,554	24,466,882	31,648,875	41,192,035
Average Account Receivables	16707539	6983777	12233441	15824437.5	20596017.5
Annual Amount (*365)	6098251735	2549078605	4465205965	5775919688	7517546388
Credit Sales	98296903	81942496	92669238	107536032	173611081
Average Collection Period	62.03910346	31.1081396	48.18433885	53.71148238	43.3010747

3) FORTE OIL

Table 4: Data on Variables relating to Forte Oil

OIL SERVICE COMPANY		FORTE OIL				
RESEARCH FACTORS	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	
Credit Revenue	117,541,434	156,714,840	108,853,855	131,613,962	86,176,010	
Trade Receivables	28,012,325	45,242,378	23,672,578	31,215,527	33,731,717	
Account Receivables Turnover Ratio	4.196061341	3.463894847	4.598310121	4.216297934	2.554747213	
Inventory	9,801,830	11250222	8971340	3816328	4,618,386	
Prepaid Expenses	107,511	127,415	125,625	112,305	475,630	
Sum	9,909,341	11,377,637	9,096,965	3,928,633	5,094,016	
Current Liabilities	52,976,418	76882658	49341673	49892291	38,232,417	
Quick Ratio	0.628466915	0.767417393	1.147995022	0.949226445	0.898957081	
current Assets	43,203,267	70378726	65740960	51287715	39,463,318	
Current Liabilities	52,976,418	76882658	49341673	49892291	38,232,417	
Current Ratio	0.815518841	0.915404434	1.332361795	1.02796873	1.032195218	
Opening Account	9,795,564	28012325	45242378	23672578	31,215,527	

Receivables					
Closing Account					
Receivables	28,012,325	45,242,378	23,672,578	31,215,527	33,731,717
Sum of Account					
Receivables	37,807,889	73,254,703	68,914,956	54,888,105	64,947,244
Average Account					
Receivables	18903944.5	36627351.5	34457478	27444052.5	32473622
Annual Amount					
(*365)	6899939743	13368983298	12576979470	10017079163	11852872030
Credit Sales	117,541,434	156714840	108853855	131613962	86,176,010
Average Collection					
Period	58.70219128	85.30770473	115.5400465	76.10954803	137.5425949

4) CAPITAL OIL

Table 5: Data on Variables relating to Capital Oil

OIL SERVICE COMPANY		CAPITAL OIL				
RESEARCH FACTORS	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	
Credit Revenue	2,967,933,461	2,106,210,044	1,132,722,975	840,383,577	471,433,034	
Trade Receivables	448,162,857	407,663,982	363,178,321	94,328,215	18,374,579	
Account Receivables Turnover Ratio	6.622444084	5.166534541	3.118916823	8.909143219	25.65680738	
Inventory	318,549	7,164,789	13,102,979	852,030	5,274,253	
Prepaid Expenses	9,720,239	15,177,398	7,786,899	3,761,574	1,844,794	
Sum	10,038,788	22,342,187	20,889,878	4,613,604	7,119,047	
Current Liabilities	256,614,641	161,623,205	154,273,277	152,418,603	141,200,751	
Quick Ratio	2.131454199	2.727964403	2.668495179	0.986875519	0.174378378	
current Assets	557,001,142	463,244,537	432,567,374	155,031,792	31,741,405	
Current Liabilities	256,614,641	161,623,205	154,273,277	152,418,603	141,200,751	
Current Ratio	2.170574289	2.866200661	2.803903452	1.017144817	0.22479629	
Opening Account						
Receivables		448,162,857	407,663,982	363,178,321	94,328,215	
Closing Account						
Receivables	448,162,857	407,663,982	363,178,321	94,328,215	18,374,579	
Sum of Account						
Receivables	448,162,857	855,826,839	770,842,303	457,506,536	112,702,794	
Average Account						
Receivables	224081428.5	427913419.5	385421151.5	228753268	56351397	
Annual Amount						
(*365)	81789721403	1.5618840E+11	1.40679E+11	83494942820	20568259905	
Credit Sales	2,967,933,461	2,106,210,044	1,132,722,975	840,383,577	471,433,034	

Average Collection Period	27.55780157	74.15613583	124.1951681	99.3533728	43.62922923
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5) MOBIL

Table 6: Data on Variables relating to Mobil

OIL SERVICE COMPANY	MOBIL				
RESEARCH FACTORS	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017
Credit Revenue	78,744,100	79,583,738	64,220,901	94,107,683	125257109
Trade Receivables	5,311,211	7,381,275	6,028,505	8,629,379	18047817
Account Receivables Turnover Ratio	14.82601614	10.78184162	10.65287347	10.90549888	6.940291394
Inventory	4,509,924	4,364,245	5878400	5071338	7948803
Prepaid Expenses	1,525,090	142,625	190,200	186,064	7435402
Sum	6,035,014	4,506,870	6,068,600	5,257,402	15,384,205
Current Liabilities	14,380,876	16,342,064	14280458	18821556	28138323
Quick Ratio	0.339054589	0.474480274	0.647508364	0.906996531	0.797399511
current Assets	10,910,916	12,260,857	15315316	22328488	37821690
Current Liabilities	14,380,876	16,342,064	14280458	18821556	28138323
Current Ratio	0.758710109	0.750263675	1.072466723	1.186325296	1.344134475
Opening Account Receivables	5,744,713	5,151,839	7342543	6028505	8829378
Closing Account Receivables	5,311,211	7,381,275	6,028,505	8,629,379	18047817
Sum of Account Receivables	11,055,924	12,533,114	13,371,048	14,657,884	26,877,195
Average Account Receivables	5527962	6266557	6685524	7328942	13438597.5
Annual Amount (*365)	2017706130	2287293305	2440216260	2675063830	4905088088
Credit Sales	78,744,100	79,583,738	64220901	94107683	125257109
Average Collection Period	25.62358488	28.74071214	37.99722866	28.42556255	39.16015727

6) TOTAL NIGERIA

Table 7: Data on Variables relating to Total Nigeria

OIL SERVICE COMPANY	TOTAL NIGERIA				
RESEARCH FACTORS	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017
Credit Revenue	238,163,160	240,618,693	208,027,688	290,952,520	288,062,650
Trade Receivables	32037595	36038378	24,630,820	48,497,566	32,726,367

Account Receivables Turnover Ratio	7.43386512	6.676734813	8.445828763	5.99932211	8.802157905
Inventory	14,640,893	19,826,763	17,391,520	34,902,844	26,666,240
Prepaid Expenses			601,653	1,527,811	571,724
Sum	14,640,893	19,826,763	17,993,173	36,430,655	27,237,964
Current Liabilities	63,159,760	78,603,987	63,949,939	113,112,861	76,938,908
Quick Ratio	0.656782705	0.642547852	0.596297629	0.621857164	0.584969454
current Assets	56,123,131	70,333,586	56,126,370	106,770,698	72,244,875
Current Liabilities	63,159,760	78,603,987	63,949,939	113,112,861	76,938,908
Current Ratio	0.888589998	0.89478395	0.87766104	0.943930664	0.938990127
Opening Account Receivables	27,883,769	32,037,595	35,789,392	24,630,820	48,497,566
Closing Account Receivables	32,037,595	36,038,378	24,630,820	48,497,566	32,726,367
Sum of Account Receivables	59,921,364	68,075,973	60,420,212	73,128,386	81,223,933
Average Account Receivables	29960682	34037986.5	30210106	36564193	40611966.5
Annual Amount (*365)	10935648930	12423865073	11026688690	13345930445	14823367773
Credit Sales	238,163,160	240,618,693	208,027,688	290,952,520	288,062,650
Average Collection Period	45.91662678	51.6330004	53.0058705	45.86978812	51.4588329

7) JAPPAUL OIL

Table 8: Data on Variables relating to Japaul Oil

OIL SERVICE COMPANY		JAPPAUL OIL				
RESEARCH FACTORS	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	
Credit Revenue	8,031,756	7,415,666	5,434,086	649,145	191,383	
Trade Receivables	1462636	13,472,412	12351478	17,328,315	8462546	
Account Receivables Turnover Ratio	5.4912883	0.550433434	0.439954312	0.037461519	0.022615298	
Inventory	13412622	120,836	12351476	42,339	34000	
Prepaid Expenses	1,668,026			21,380	31,219	
Sum	15,080,648	120,836	12,351,476	63,719	65,219	
Current Liabilities	5,022,969	7,264,915	5,764,759	15,655,088	9899218	
Quick Ratio	0.5342695	1.906550593	0.075075818	1.122525533	0.860171783	
current Assets	17,764,267	13,971,764	12,784,270	17,636,955	8580247	

Current Liabilities	5,022,969	7,264,915	5,764,759	15,655,088	9899218
Current Ratio	3.5366069	1.92318341	2.217659056	1.126595711	0.866760081
Opening Account Receivables	1,215,458	13,412,622	14,623,211	12,351,476	17328315
Closing Account Receivables	1,462,636	13,472,412	12,351,478	17,328,315	8462546
Sum of Account Receivables	2,678,094	26,885,034	26,974,689	29,679,791	25,790,861
Average Account Receivables	1339047	13442517	13487344.5	14839895.5	12895430.5
Annual Amount (*365)	488752155	4906518705	4922880743	5416561858	4706832133
Credit Sales	8,031,756	7,415,666	5,434,086	649,145	191,383
Average Collection Period	60.852466	661.6423535	905.9261746	8344.147852	24593.78384

8) OANDO PLC.

Table 9: Data on Variables relating to Oando Plc.

OIL SERVICE COMPANY		OANDO PLC				
RESEARCH FACTORS	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	
Credit Revenue	5,883,304	14,217,468	161,489,950	4,858,182	497,422,483	
Trade Receivables	125,073,570	176,868,029	206042583	111396694	141588922	
Account Receivables Turnover Ratio	0.047038747	0.080384613	0.78376978	0.043611546	3.513145492	
Inventory						
Prepaid Expenses	892,493	138,179	147,313	3,174,809	1289580	
Sum	892,493	138,179	147,313	3,174,809	1,289,580	
Current Liabilities	143,841,084	244,480,650	241039854	107861344	137032399	
Quick Ratio	0.88107112	0.735852261	0.863399175	1.105696773	1.040370533	
current Assets	127,626,718	180,039,818	208260924	122436749	143854050	
Current Liabilities	143,841,084	244,480,650	241039854	107861344	137032399	
Current Ratio	0.887275836	0.736417455	0.864010331	1.135130942	1.0497813	
Opening Account Receivables		125,073,570	210616369	206042583	111396694	
Closing Account Receivables	125,073,570	176,868,029	206,042,583	111,396,694	141588922	
Sum of Account Receivables	125,073,570	301,941,599	416,658,952	317,439,277	252,985,616	
Average Account	62536785	150970799.5	208329476	158719638.5	126492808	

Receivables					
Annual Amount (*365)	22825926525	55104341818	76040258740	57932668053	46169874920
Credit Sales	5,883,304	14,217,468	161,489,950	4,858,182	497,422,483
Average Collection Period	3879.780226	3875.819648	470.866817	11924.76281	92.81823098

9) MRS OIL PLC.

Table 10: Data on Variables relating to Mrs Oil Plc.

OIL SERVICE COMPANY		MRS OIL PLC				
RESEARCH FACTORS	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	
Credit Revenue	87,786,323	92,325,405	87,099,216	109,635,054	107088347	
Trade Receivables	22,459,632	21975262	20519974	43244878	34234991	
Account Receivables Turnover Ratio	3.908626953	4.201333527	4.244606548	2.535214783	3.128037831	
Inventory	7,723,595	3,822,749	6260483	7004173	5289372	
Prepaid Expenses		393,988	289,191	333,130	309862	
Sum	7,723,595	4,216,737	6,549,674	7,337,303	5,599,234	
Current Liabilities	40,068,319	32,090,288	40591700	54070179	36914144	
Quick Ratio	0.887840041	1.030251925	1.008425466	1.011077529	1.043859096	
current Assets	43,297,853	37,277,818	47483378	62006446	44132399	
Current Liabilities	40,068,319	32,090,288	40591700	54070179	36914144	
Current Ratio	1.080600686	1.161654205	1.169780472	1.146777154	1.195541714	
Opening Account Receivables	18,564,945	22,459,632	20636012	20519974	43244878	
Closing Account Receivables	22,459,632	21,975,262	20,519,974	43,244,878	34234991	
Sum of Account Receivables	41,024,577	44,434,894	41,155,986	63,764,852	77,479,869	
Average Account Receivables	20512288.5	22217447	20577993	31882426	38739934.5	
Annual Amount (*365)	7486985303	8109368155	7510967445	11637085490	14140076093	
Credit Sales	87,786,323	92,325,405	87099216	109635054	107088347	
Average Collection Period	85.28646658	87.83463398	86.23461599	106.1438387	132.041221	

10) SEPLAT PETROLEUM

Table 11: Data on Variables relating to Seplat Petroleum

OIL SERVICE COMPANY		SEPLAT PETROLEUM				
RESEARCH FACTORS	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	
Credit Revenue	136,658	124,377	98,593	51,995	127,655	
Trade Receivables	63,699	198,101	262,874	326,046	327,528	
Account Receivables Turnover Ratio	2.145371	0.627846	0.375058	0.159471363	0.389752937	
Inventory	6,713	10,027	15,681	31,295	29,576	
Prepaid Expenses	16,960	24,225	2,123	1,983	513	
Sum	23,673	34,252	17,804	33,278	30,089	
Current Liabilities	68,458	136,120	243,619	153,109	217,829	
Quick Ratio	1.066917	1.672142	1.356196	2.423084208	2.041729981	
current Assets	96,712	261,864	348,199	404,274	474,837	
Current Liabilities	68,458	136,120	243,619	153,109	217,829	
Current Ratio	1.41272	1.923773	1.429277	2.640432633	2.179861267	
Opening Account Receivables		63,699	229,279	262,874	326,046	
Closing Account Receivables	63,699	198,101	262,874	326,046	327,528	
Sum of Account Receivables	63,699	261,800	492,153	588,920	653,574	
Average Account Receivables	31849.5	130900	246076.5	294460	326787	
Annual Amount (*365)	11625068	47778500	89817923	107477900	119277255	
Credit Sales	136,658	124,377	98,593	51,995	127,655	
Average Collection Period	85.06686	384.1426	910.997	2067.08145	934.3719792	

Since the figures drawn represent business affairs for a year's period, the Average Collection Period (ACP) are thus measured in days. This signifies that for the respective credit remittances to the various companies, the generated figures tell by how many days credits remain uncollected before being redeemed. It is worthy of note here that the shorter the days taken to recover monies owed the company by its debtors, the better for their financial states.

The Accounts Receivables Ratios (ARR) given evaluate the capability of each company to efficiently collect funds from its trade debtors when the debts fall due, as well as how well it grants credit to its customers. A high ratio here is more to be desired than a low one.

The Current Ratios (CR) derived signifies whether the companies have enough short-term assets to cover its immediate liabilities without selling inventory. Here as well, a high ratio is better preferred to a low one.

The Quick Ratios (QR) indicate the companies' ability to meet their current liabilities as they become due, given that the company's inventory and prepaid expenses are excluded. A high ratio is better than a low one.

Next, the table below indicates the total and the on-average rating for each of the variables.

Table 12: Summary Data for Analysis

YEAR	INDEPENDENT VARIABLES		DEPENDENT VARIABLES	
	ACP	ART	CR	QR
2013	444	6.13	1.41	0.91
2014	540	4.80	1.37	1.20
2015	291	4.07	1.43	1.07
2016	2,168	4.61	1.28	1.14
2017	2,614	6.17	1.13	0.96

4.2. Research Results Derived

Analyses and the results thereof are here drawn from computations via the Statistical Packages for Social Sciences (SPSS). Here, we shall have our measures of central tendencies (Mean, Median, Mode), Measures of dispersion, Bivariate Pearson Product Moment Correlation, Regression models, and Analysis of Variance (ANOVA). Accordingly, our research analysis makes the underneath applicable:

4.2.1. Measures of Central Tendencies & Dispersion

Our measures of central tendencies as well as measures of dispersion are thus analyzed and tabulated hereunder:

Table 13: Computation of Measures of Central Tendencies and Measures of Dispersion.

		Statistics					
		Statistic	Bootstrap ^b				
			Bias	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval		
					Lower	Upper	
N	Valid	ACP	5	0	0	5	5
		ART	5	0	0	5	5
		CR	5	0	0	5	5
		QR	5	0	0	5	5
	Missing	ACP	0	0	0	0	0
		ART	0	0	0	0	0
		CR	0	0	0	0	0
		QR	0	0	0	0	0
Mean	ACP	1211.4000	-22.1388	431.6613	396.6803	2060.2000	
	ART	5.1560	-.0092	.3756	4.3791	5.8720	
	CR	1.3240	.0019	.0479	1.2200	1.4100	
	QR	1.0560	-.0015	.0474	.9660	1.1500	
Median	ACP	540.0000	487.7500	825.6854	291.0000	2614.0000	
	ART	4.8000	.3429	.7134	4.0700	6.1700	
	CR	1.3700	-.0197	.0725	1.1300	1.4300	
	QR	1.0700	-.0172	.0789	.9100	1.2000	
Mode	ACP	291.00 ^a					
	ART	4.07 ^a					

	CR	1.13 ^a				
	QR	.91 ^a				
Std. Deviation	ACP	1091.92344	-155.54808	291.13134	101.90289	1245.99226
	ART	.94619	-.11309	.21154	.27532	1.14303
	CR	.12280	-.01843	.03912	.02449	.16087
	QR	.12095	-.01655	.02634	.04245	.14622
Variance	ACP	1192296.800	-230910.048	393665.718	10384.200	1552496.700
	ART	.895	-.157	.303	.076	1.307
	CR	.015	-.003	.007	.001	.026
	QR	.015	-.003	.005	.002	.021
Minimum	ACP	291.00				
	ART	4.07				
	CR	1.13				
	QR	.91				
Maximum	ACP	2614.00				
	ART	6.17				
	CR	1.43				
	QR	1.20				

a. Multiple modes exist. The smallest value is shown

b. Unless otherwise noted, bootstrap results are based on 500 bootstrap samples

Our above measures included both measures of central tendencies and measures of dispersion: the mean distribution, median, mode, standard deviation, variance, minimum and maximum values. The results shown are based on the data from the averages in the variables table above. The table shows the individual behaviours as well as the summary statistics of the data used for the study between 2013 and 2017 within which relevant data could be sourced. Consistent with the table, we conclude that our estimates are statistically significant at the 95% level of confidence.

4.2.2. Bivariate Pearson Product Moment Correlation

Table 14: Table of Values for Bivariate Pearson Product Moment Correlation.

		Correlations					
		ACP	ART	CR	QR		
ACP	Pearson Correlation	1	.337	-.948*	-.098		
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.580	.014	.875		
	Sum of Squares and Cross-products	4769187.200	1391.058	-508.638	-51.822		
	Covariance	1192296.800	347.765	-127.160	-12.956		
	N	5	5	5	5		
	Bootstrap ^c	Bias	0	-.037	-.013	.044	
		Std. Error	0	.491	.033	.513	
		95% Confidence Interval	Lower	1	-.764	-1.000	-.892
			Upper	1	1.000	-.883	1.000
	ART	Pearson Correlation	.337	1	-.474	-.769	
Sig. (2-tailed)		.580		.420	.129		
Sum of Squares and Cross-products		1391.058	3.581	-.220	-.352		
Covariance		347.765	.895	-.055	-.088		
N		5	5	5	5		

Table 15: Multiple Regression table.

The Model (M) Summaries ^{a,b}									
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics				
					R Square Change	F Change	df1	df2	Sig. F Change
1.	.963a	.926	.853	.04711	.926	12.592	2	2	.074
2.	.787b	.620	.240	.10545	.620	1.631	2	2	.380
R ^a ; Predictors: (Constant), ART, ACP					R ^b ; Predictors: (Constant), ART, ACP				
M ^a ; Dependent Variable: CR					M ^b ; Dependent Variable: QR				

multiple regression models produced correlation (R) values of 0.963 and 0.787 respectively upon computation of the effect relationship in each case between the dependent variable (CR) and the independent variables (ART & ACP); and between the dependent variable (QR) and the independent variables (ART & ACP). These represent positive linear relationships between predicted and explanatory variables. The models similarly produced positive determinants in terms of R-square (Co-efficient of Determination) in the values of 0.926 and 0.620 which were adjusted for errors to 0.853 and 0.240. These show that the independent variables explain only 9.26% and 6.20% in the main and 8.53% and 2.40% (as adjusted), of the changes in liquidity position as measured by CR and QR respectively.

Our table of coefficients follows hence, showing the individual effect of each independent variable on liquidity given that the other independent variable is held constant:

Table 16: Correlation Coefficient Table.

Model	Coefficients ^{a,b}										
	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.	95.0% Confidence Interval for B		Correlations			
	B	Std. Error				Lower Bound	Upper Bound	Zero-order	Partial	Part	
1	(Constant)	1.562	.131	11.896	.007	.997	2.127				
	ACP	.000	.000	-.889	-4.367	.049	.000	.000	-.948	-.951	-.838
	ART	-.023	.026	-.175	-.858	.481	-.136	.091	-.474	-.519	-.165
2	(Constant)	1.579	.294	5.369	.033	.314	2.843				
	ACP	-.005	.000	.181	.391	.733	.000	.000	-.098	.267	.171
	ART	-.106	.059	-.830	-1.792	.215	-.361	.149	-.769	-.785	-.781
a. Dependent Variable: CR											
b. Dependent Variable: QR											

The coefficient table above is derived computing our multiple regression equations. From equation (1), when other factors (Average Collection Period [ACP] and Accounts Receivable Turnover [ART]) are held constant, the liquidity measure (Current Ratio [CR]) will be 1.562. Furthermore, holding ACP constant, a unit increase in ART would lead to a 0.023 (2.3%) decrease in Current Ratio as a measure of liquidity.

Again, holding ART constant, a unit increase in ACP would result in no change at all to Current Ratio as a measure of liquidity.

From equation (2), when the independent variables (Average Collection Period [ACP] and Accounts Receivable Turnover [ART]) are at zero, the Quick Ratio (QR) measure will be 1.579. With ACP held constant, a unit increase in ART would lead to a 0.106 (10.6%) decrease in the Quick Ratio proxy. Similarly, holding ART constant, a unit increase in ACP would lead to a 0.005 (0.5%) decrease in Quick Ratio as a measure of liquidity.

4.2.4. Analysis of Variance (ANOVA)

Finally, our Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) table is presented below:

Table 17: Analysis of Variance table.

		ANOVA ^{a,b}				
Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	.056	2	.028	12.592	.074a
	Residual	.004	2	.002		
	Total	.060	4			
2	Regression	.036	2	.018	1.631	.380b
	Residual	.022	2	.011		
	Total	.059	4			

a. Predictors: (Constant), ACP, ART. Computation in respect of CR.

b. Predictors: (Constant), ACP, ART. Computation in respect of QR.

The analysis of variance (ANOVA) refers to the partitioning of the total variance in a set of data into a number of component parts, so that the relative contributions of identifiable sources of variation to the total variation in measured responses can be determined.

Drawing from the ANOVA table above, we can summarize by saying that the models are significant owing to F-test values of 0.315 and 0.400, at significance values of 12.592 and 1.631 respectively.

5. DISCUSSION

As aforementioned, our table showing the bivariate pearson product moment correlation would be our basis for advancing findings on this relationship-based research. The researchers also thought it wise to bring up our previously stated hypotheses and analyze results discovered relevant and peculiar in addressing each. Hence, we have:

5.1. Hypothesis One & Decision

HO1: The Average Collection period of Oil Service Companies have no significant relationship with their Current Ratios as a measure of Liquidity

Decision Rule:

- Accept H_1 (and reject H_0) if the correlation coefficient of ACP is positively or negatively signed in relation to CR and statistically significant ((i.e. correlation coefficient is $>$ or $<$ 0).
- Accept H_0 (and reject H_1) if the correlation coefficient of ACP is statistically insignificant (i.e. correlation is $=0$).

Analysis of Pearson Correlation Values:

Table 18: Extract from Correlation table relating ACP to CR.

		ACP	ART	CR	QR	
ACP	Pearson Correlation	1	.337	-.948*	-.098	
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.580	.014	.875	
	Sum of Squares and Cross-products	4769187.200	1391.058	-508.638	-51.822	
	Covariance	1192296.800	347.765	-127.160	-12.956	
	N	5	5	5	5	
Bootstrap ^c	Bias	0	-.037	-.013	.044	
	Std. Error	0	.491	.033	.513	
	95% Confidence Interval	Lower	1	-.764	-1.000	-.892
		Upper	1	1.000	-.883	1.000

The table above presents the relationship between Average Collection Period (ACP) and Current Ratios (CR). As seen in the table, the correlation coefficient estimate of ACP in relation to CR is -0.948 showing that the variables have a negative relationship, with ART as a control variable. The result indicates that an increase in ACP by one unit decreases the organization's liquidity position by 0.948 million naira, on average, per annum.

Decision:

Since the correlation coefficient of the ACP variable is negatively signed and statistically significant at the 95% level of confidence, we reject H₀ and accordingly accept H₁.

5.2. Hypothesis Two & Decision

HO₂: The Account Receivables Turnover of Oil Service Companies have no significant relationship with their Quick Ratios as a measure of Liquidity;

Decision Rule:

- Accept H₁ (and reject H₀) if the correlation coefficient of ART is positively or negatively signed in relation to QR and statistically significant ((i.e. correlation coefficient is > or < 0).
- Accept H₀ (and reject H₁) if the correlation coefficient of ART is statistically insignificant (i.e. correlation is =0).

Analysis of Pearson Correlation Values

Table 19: Extract from Correlation table relating ART to QR

		ACP	ART	CR	QR	
ART	Pearson Correlation	.337	1	-.474	-.769	
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.580		.420	.129	
	Sum of Squares and Cross-products	1391.058	3.581	-.220	-.352	
	Covariance	347.765	.895	-.055	-.088	
	N	5	5	5	5	
Bootstrap ^c	Bias	-.037	0	.099	.062	
	Std. Error	.491	0	.520	.451	
	95% Confidence Interval	Lower	-.764	1	-1.000	-1.000
		Upper	1.000	1	.880	1.000

The table above represents the relationship between Account Receivables Turnover (ART) and Quick Ratios (QR). As seen in the table, the correlation coefficient of ART in relation to QR is -0.769 showing that the variables have a negative relationship, with ACP as a control variable. The result indicates that an increase in ART by one unit decreases the organization’s liquidity by 0.769 million naira, on average, per annum.

Decision:

Since the correlation coefficient of the ART variable is negatively signed and statistically significant at the 95% level of confidence, we reject H0 and accordingly accept H1.

5.3. Hypothesis Three & Decision

HO3: The Average Collection Period of Oil Service Companies have no significant relationship with their Quick Ratios as a measure of Liquidity

Decision Rule:

- Accept H₁ (and reject H₀) if the correlation coefficient of ACP is positively or negatively signed in relation to QR and statistically significant ((i.e. correlation coefficient is > or < 0).
- Accept H₀ (and reject H₁) if the correlation coefficient of ACP is statistically insignificant (i.e. correlation is =0).

Analysis of Pearson Correlation Values

Table 20: Extract from Correlation table relating ACP to QR.

		ACP	ART	CR	QR	
ACP	Pearson Correlation	1	.337	-.948*	-.098	
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.580	.014	.875	
	Sum of Squares and Cross-products	4769187.200	1391.058	-508.638	-51.822	
	Covariance	1192296.800	347.765	-127.160	-12.956	
	N	5	5	5	5	
Bootstrap ^c	Bias	0	-.037	-.013	.044	
	Std. Error	0	.491	.033	.513	
	95% Confidence Interval	Lower	1	-.764	-1.000	-.892
		Upper	1	1.000	-.883	1.000

The table presents the relationship between Average Collection Period (ACP) and Quick Ratios (QR). As revealed from the table, the correlation coefficient of ACP in relation to QR is -0.098 showing that the variables have a negative relationship, with ART as a control variable. The result indicates that an increase in ACP by one unit decreases the organization’s Liquidity by 0.098 million naira, on average, per annum.

Decision:

Since the correlation coefficient of the ACP variable is negatively signed and statistically significant at the 95% level of confidence, we reject H0 and accordingly accept H1.

5.4. Hypothesis Four & Decision

HO4: The Account Receivables Turnover of Oil Service Companies have no significant relationship with their Current Ratios as a measure of Liquidity.

Decision Rule:

- Accept H₁ (and reject H₀) if the correlation coefficient of ART is positively or negatively signed in relation to CR and statistically significant ((i.e. correlation coefficient is > or < 0).
- Accept H₀ (and reject H₁) if the correlation coefficient of ART is statistically insignificant (i.e. correlation is =0).

Analysis of Pearson Correlation Values

Table 21: Extract from Correlation table relating ART to CR.

	ACP	ART	CR	QR
Pearson Correlation	.337	1	-.474	-.769
Sig. (2-tailed)	.580		.420	.129
Sum of Squares and Cross-products	1391.058	3.581	-.220	-.352
Covariance	347.765	.895	-.055	-.088
ART N	5	5	5	5
Bias	-.037	0	.099	.062
Bootstrap Std. Error	.491	0	.520	.451
95% Confidence Interval	Lower	-.764	1	-1.000
	Upper	1.000	1	.880

The table presents the relationship between Account Receivables Turnover (ART) and Current Ratio (CR). As shown in the table above, the correlation coefficient of ART in relation to CR is -0.474 showing that the variables have a negative relationship, with ACP as a control variable. The result indicates that an increase in ART by one unit decreases the organization's liquidity by 0.474 million naira, on average, per annum.

Decision:

Since the correlation coefficient of the ART variable is negatively signed and statistically significant at the 95% level of confidence, we reject H0 and accordingly accept H1.

6. SUMMARY & CONCLUSION

6.1. Summary

This study has empirically examined the relationship between Trade Receivables Management and Organizations' Liquidity in Nigeria, with a survey of some 10 Oil Servicing companies over a 5 year period (2013 to 2017). The study explored financial reports of these companies in denominations of income statement and Statement of Financial Position. In an effort to address the problems of the study and contribute to the emergent body of academic literature on this all-important topic, four null hypotheses were formulated. The study reviewed relevant literatures on the subject, with proper consideration of certain vital, especially those holding our conceptual structure. To analyze the secondary data collected from the annual reports and accounts of the sampled oil servicing companies, correlational research design and panel multiple regression techniques were used. Given at the 95% level of confidence, the study established statistically negative relationships existing between measures of the dependent and independent variables in all cases.

6.2. Conclusion

In the whole, the researchers, based on analyses, conclude thus:

- The Average Collection period of Oil Service Companies has a negative significant relationship with their Current Ratios as a measure of Liquidity.
- The Account Receivables Turnover of Oil Service Companies has a negative significant relationship with their Quick Ratios as a measure of Liquidity.
- The Average Collection Period of Oil Service Companies has a negative significant relationship with their Quick Ratios as a measure of Liquidity; and
- The Account Receivables Turnover of Oil Service Companies has a negative significant relationship with their Current Ratios as a measure of Liquidity.

7. RECOMMENDATIONS

Consistent with the researchers' analyses:

- a. Oil servicing companies should establish tested and trusted mechanisms for realizing trade receivables within the year in order to boost their current ratio position.
- b. Drawing from our multiple regression model, holding ACP constant, a unit increase in ART would lead to a 0.023 (2.3%) decrease in Current Ratio as a measure of liquidity. Again, holding ART constant, a unit increase in ACP would result in no change at all to Current Ratio as a measure of liquidity. Oil servicing companies should focus more on reducing the number of days they have to wait before realizing their receivables. ART makes no change at all to current ratio position and as such poses any threat at all.
- c. Still drawing from our regression model, when the independent variables (Average Collection Period [ACP] and Accounts Receivable Turnover [ART]) are at zero, the Quick Ratio (QR) measure will be 1.579. With ACP held constant, a unit increase in ART would lead to a 0.106 (10.6%) decrease in the Quick Ratio proxy. Similarly, holding ART constant, a unit increase in ACP would lead to a 0.005 (0.5%) decrease in Quick Ratio. Both ACP AND ART ought to be improved upon but more focus should be placed on ART since an increase in this variable brings about a greater 10.6% decrease in quick ratio than the 0.5% decrease brought about by a unit increase in ACP.

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